

Residual effect on succeeding winter rice of urea applied to summer rice

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We studied the residual effect of different slow-release urea forms applied to Jun-Oct rice (ADT36) on the succeeding Oct-Feb rice (IR20) in 1986-88.

The soil was a clay loam with 254-13.4-113.7 kg NPK/ha. The N materials used for the short-duration summer rice were urea supergranule, sulfur-coated urea, neem cake urea, gypsum-coated urea, rock phosphate-coated urea, and prilled urea (PU) at 0, 37.5, 75.0, 112.5, and 150.0 kg N/ha. Half of the recommended N (50 kg/ha) as PU was applied to the succeeding winter rice in three splits: 50+11+21.

Soil analysis after harvest of summer

Residual effect of urea forms on winter rice. Aduthurai, India, 1986-88.

Treatment	Summer rice grain yield (t/ha)		Available soil N (kg/ha)		Winter rice grain yield (t/ha)	
	1986-87	1987-88	1986-87	1987-88	1986-87	1987-88
<i>N level (kg/ha)</i>						
0	4.3	4.3	229.8	239.5	3.1	3.7
37.5	5.3	5.6	252.0	248.1	3.1	4.1
75.0	6.2	6.1	249.8	247.8	2.6	3.7
112.5	6.7	6.7	264.0	258.8	3.0	4.1
150.0	6.7	6.7	262.0	254.1	3.2	3.6
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.2	ns	ns	ns	ns
<i>Forms of urea</i>						
Prilled urea	5.9	6.3	258.0	252.3	2.9	4.1
Urea supergranule	6.0	6.4	241.3	243.2	3.1	4.0
Sulfur-coated urea	6.0	—	258.5	253.2	3.2	—
Neem cake-coated urea	6.8	6.4	249.3	251.4	2.9	3.9
Gypsum-coated urea	5.8	6.2	251.5	247.1	3.0	3.6
Rock phosphate urea	5.7	6.1	250.5	252.0	3.1	3.8
Plastic-coated urea	—	6.3	—	250.2	—	3.8
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.1	ns	ns	ns	ns

rice showed no significant difference in available soil N due to form or level of urea. Winter rice as a residual crop did not show any yield response to urea form or N level (see table).

We infer that slow-release urea materials did not leave any residue in the field after 110 d (period between urea basal application and postharvest soil sampling). □

SOCIOECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

Livelihood

Energy use in rice - wheat cropping system

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We estimated the energy used in various cultural operations for a rice - wheat sequence with recommended and low input levels at Birsa Agricultural University Farm, Kanke, Ranchi, 1984-86.

At the recommended inputs, rice variety Sita was transplanted the second week of Jul at 15- × 10-cm spacing; wheat cultivar Sonalika was sown the

third week of Nov (22 rows). Both crops received 100-2-25 kg NPK/ha and adequate plant protection.

At low inputs, rice and wheat were sown 15 d later with 25% lower plant density, 50% less fertilizer, and only seed treatment plus one hand weeding.

Rice received one irrigation at flowering and 106 cm monsoon rain during vegetative growth. Wheat received four irrigations and only 4.7 cm rainfall.

Data on direct and indirect sources of energy were obtained from the equivalent energy values of inputs and outputs (Table 1). Energy output through grain yield together with energy use efficiency (output/input ratio) and energy productivity were estimated.

Energy input and output data for rice and wheat at recommended and low input levels are presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Equivalent direct and indirect sources of energy. West Bengal, India.

Energy source	Unit	Equivalent energy (MJ)
<i>Input</i>		
Human labor - adult man	h	1.96
adult woman	h	1.57
Bullocks (medium)	Pair/h	10.10
Diesel fuel	Liter	56.31
Fertilizer N	kg	60.60
P	kg	24.98
K	kg	8.04
Seed - Rice	kg	14.80
Wheat	kg	14.40
Pesticide - Aldrin 5% dust	kg	10.00
BHC 5% dust	kg	10.00
Butachlor (Punch-G)	kg	10.00
Dimethoate 35 EC	kg	120.00
Agrosan GN	kg	120.00
Isoproturon (Taurus-50)	kg	120.00
Irrigation	cm/ha	46.02
<i>Output</i>		
Rice	kg	14.80
Wheat	kg	14.40

Table 2. Energy inputs and outputs in rice - wheat production.^a West Bengal, India.

Energy use	Inputs and outputs (MJ/ha)			
	Rice		Wheat	
	Recommended inputs	Low inputs	Recommended inputs	Low inputs
Land preparation	1,689.9 (13.5)	1,689.9 (20.7)	1,546.8 (11.4)	1,546.8 (16.6)
Seed and sowing or transplanting	2,338.3 (18.8)	1,840.4 (22.6)	2,127.0 (15.7)	1,767.0 (19.0)
Fertilizer and application	6,870.9 (55.1)	3,433.4 (42.1)	6,903.8 (50.9)	3,451.9 (37.1)
Plant protection	616.9 (4.9)	302.0 (3.7)	467.4 (3.4)	192.1 (2.1)
Irrigation	349.6 (2.8)	349.6 (4.3)	1,398.6 (10.3)	1,398.6 (15.0)
Harvesting and threshing	591.9 (4.8)	536.2 (6.6)	1,120.2 (8.2)	942.0 (10.1)
Total energy input	12,457.5	8,151.5	13,563.8	9,298.4
Total energy output	62,569.9	56,682.6	47,809.7	4,0610.5
Energy output:input ratio	5.02	6.95	3.52	4.37
Energy productivity (g/MJ)	390.1	407.9	260.4	256.2

^aFigures in parentheses indicate percentage of total energy input.

Chemical fertilizer is the major energy input. Seed, sowing/ transplanting, and land preparation are the next most important energy inputs.

Total energy input and total energy output were higher with recommended inputs, energy use efficiency was greatest with low inputs. Energy productivity was not affected by low inputs. □

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The Alley Farming Network for Tropical Africa (AFNETA) commenced operations 1 Feb 1989. Its objectives are to promote alley farming research and on-farm testing in different environments.

AFNETA is cosponsored by IITA, ILCA, and ICRAF. Collaborators are scientists in national agricultural research systems.

Correspondence can be addressed to the network, c/o IITA, Oyo Road, PMB 5320, Ibadan, Nigeria (Cable:

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New IRRI publications

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Weeds reported in rice in South and Southeast Asia, by K.M. Moody
A guide to creating self-learning materials, by D.R. Minnick
World rice statistics 1987

IPM Newsletter discontinued

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ERRATUM

Using silica gel desiccant to dry rough rice samples, by P. A. Clarke and M. A. Quasem. 14(2) (Apr 89), p. 14.

The regression equation in paragraph 3 should read:

$$Y = 4.17X^{0.38}; r=0.91, p=0.01. \square$$